

Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing: a Critical Review

Soil Moisture Measurements by Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing: a Critical Review

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Abstract

Soil moisture information is crucial for water management in agricultural and hydrological systems. Several measurement methods exist on multiple scales, however, poorly harmonized. Despite its significance this lack of precision marginalized the topologically complex assessment of soil water. In addition, there is an urgent need for real-time, high-quality, temporally and spatially consistent data on soil moisture. Such are needed to optimise water management strategies as well as climate change monitoring, modelling and mitigation. Over the last decade, Cosmic-Ray Neutron probes have been recognized as a promising tool for soil moisture measurements due to the large footprint of several hectares and half a meter in depth. Using this technique one can relate the flux density of above-ground neutrons generated by cosmic-ray induced air showers to the amount of water in the environment. Its strengths are the non-invasive nature of the method and the low-maintenance sensors. National and international monitoring networks like COSMOS, COSMOS-UK, ADAPTER and TERENO sites are on the forefront of integrating these sensors into their monitoring program. To address the need of harmonization of this new methodology, the 'Soil Moisture Metrology' (SoMMet) consortium establishes the metrological basis of the Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing and its chain of traceability. Initially, Cosmic-Ray Neutron instruments had relied on the use of the scarce helium-3. In order to scale up the method and to reduce costs, research groups in Europe have developed instruments using alternative technologies including readout electronics and data acquisition systems. With a more cost-efficient instrumentation the initial focus on hydrological research Cosmic-Ray Neutron instruments emerge into applied contexts. Examples are irrigation management and soil moisture mapping for climate-resilient agriculture. Still, challenges arise especially for irrigated fields with a size smaller than the footprint or heterogeneous conditions, especially biomass distribution.

Keywords: Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing, Water, Soil Moisture Measurement, Neutron Detector, Environmental Monitoring, Hydrology, Neutron Transport

1. Introduction

Soil moisture regulates land-atmosphere exchanges and is essential for understanding and predicting terrestrial water and energy dynamics as it is strongly coupled with air temperature, evapotranspiration and precipitation [1, 2]. Soil moisture has been classified as an Essential Climate Variable (ECV) by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) in support of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) [3]. Understanding water dynamics and abundance in soil is one key factor in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 6, 13 and 15, which address their role Climatology, management practices and conservation of nature [4, 5]. In recent

decades, advances have been made in establishing global soil moisture observation systems, such as the ISMN data base [6] which currently mainly rely on in-situ measurements. Nevertheless, variability in soil-water storage is still poorly captured by various spatio-temporal scales and for many regions of the world. For a long time, soil moisture was only measured locally (i.e. on the point-scale), which are accurate, but not representative for heterogeneous landscapes [7]. On the other hand, remote sensing products [8] typically only have access to the first few centimeters of land surface at considerably long revisit times more coarse resolution usually on the kilometer scale [9, 10]. Additionally, biases, especially those for densely vegetated areas and complex terrain, impede the interpretation of remotely sensed changes in water storage [11]. Water dynamics in soils rarely can be described on the 'remote-sensing' scale. Instead, runoff generation, groundwater recharge, and water availability to plants are predominantly driven on the scale of catchments and smaller

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Figure 1: Sensor installation of a CRNS instrument in an agricultural context.

hydrological units. A better understanding of the dynamics on such scales is thus essential for flood- and weather prediction as well as water resource- and landscape management. This review builds on [12] by enriching the CRNS methodology and expanding the state of the art. The field has since matured from a developing technique to a quantitative geophysical tool. Within the first seven years covered by [12] around 50 papers had been published within the field of Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing, after another seven years further 200 publications had been added. This maturation is characterized by three developments: a deepened theoretical understanding of the neutron physics, leading to more complex and physically advanced correction formalisms, significant advances in detector technology and progress in the use of simulation tools that allow for precise signal quantification necessary for applications in complex real-world examples.

2. The CRNS Method

Cosmic-ray neutron sensing (CRNS) is a novel method for non-invasive soil moisture measurements. It relies on determining the neutron flux in the epithermal-to-fast energy range, typically in intervals from minutes to hours. The main component is the cosmic-ray neutron sensor, or often referred to as probe (CRP or CRNP), which operates continuously above ground to produce time series at a fixed location or to spatially map a region while in motion, see for example Fig. 1. The change in the neutron count rate of the detector allows to deduce the amount of water within a representative volume around the sensor location. Thereby, either gravimetric or volumetric soil moisture can be inferred. Soil water is by far the largest contributor to the signal, other contributions from air humidity or biomass (carbohydrates) are minor correction factors. As the method is sensitive to hydrogen in any type of molecule, CRNS also measures chemically bound water or snow. These quantities may need to be subtracted from the signal in order to obtain the soil water content alone. Unlike other methods CRNS does not significantly depend on the soil chemistry or texture. In contrast to the similar nuclear gauges [13, 14] using neutrons with epithermal energies and above makes the method practically not susceptible to small amounts of absorbers in the soil [15].

The cosmic-ray neutron spectrum spans several orders of magnitude in energy and consists of four physically distinct domains. These are depicted in Fig. 2 with the intensity in $E d\Phi/dE$ yielding usually between 50 and 200 neutrons per square meter

Figure 2: Simulated cosmic-ray neutron spectrum. The incoming spectrum (shaded gray) and resulting above-ground neutron intensities (in arbitrary units) are shown for dry (orange) and moist conditions (blue), both at an air humidity of 1 g/m^3 . The epithermal region with largest intensity ratios between dry and moist marks the hydrogen-sensitive domain. Neutrons with energies between 0.3 eV and 30 keV are most suitable as a proxy for the environmental hydrogen content. The cosmic-ray probe detection probability (CRP, green) is designed to cover that range.

and second. Atmospheric cascades, induced by primary cosmic rays [16, 17], generate different species of particles, among them neutrons, with energies ranging up to several hundred MeV. Consecutively, evaporation neutrons [18], with kinetic energies of a few MeV, are produced if atomic nuclei in the soil and atmosphere become excited through interactions and subsequently emit particles [19]. At specific nuclear resonances, specific to the composition of protons and neutrons within an isotope, reaction probabilities are increased significantly. These processes result in a distinct resonance structure superimposed to the evaporation peak. The dominant further reaction for neutrons is elastic scattering. For each interaction a fraction of kinetic energy gets lost, depending on the mass of the collision partner. Scattering is most efficient when the target is a proton, as in hydrogen, because both particles have the same mass [20]. On average the moderation (slowing down) of neutrons by water requires 18 collisions [21]. For heavier atomic nuclei, the number of required interactions can be ten times greater. On a logarithmic energy scale, this behavior appears in the above-ground cosmic-ray neutron spectrum as the epithermal plateau. The slowing-down efficiency correlates with neutron density in the epither-

Figure 3: Timeline of important steps in CRNS methodology along with major scientific CRNS instrument networks.

mal range. Since hydrogen efficiently moderates neutrons, the flux in this region serves as a proxy for environmental hydrogen content. On the lower end of the spectrum neutrons have reached thermal equilibrium with their surrounding - on average their kinetic energy equals that of the collision partner. At this stage, energy loss and gain during collisions balance out, halting further slowing down. In the thermal region absorption becomes a relevant process, particularly by elements such as nitrogen [22], and the neutron transport is terminated. For high-energy neutrons their mean free path in air can exceed 100 m. That length decreases with lower kinetic energies to around 10 m for thermal neutrons [23]. This makes the flux density above the ground representative for soil moisture at these scales.

CRNS instruments are designed to match this epithermal-to-fast energy range with their sensitivity. Such a typical CRP response function is shown in Fig. 2. While suppression of the thermal contribution to the signal is possible using shielding materials containing neutron absorbers, a partial sensitivity to high energy neutrons cannot be avoided [24]. Cosmic-ray detectors therefore resemble mid-sized channels of a Bonner Sphere Spectrometer [25, 26].

2.1. Historical Development

Since the discovery of the neutron [27, 28, 29], hydrogen and especially water are known for their exceptional strength for slowing down neutrons. From the 1940s on active neutron sources were used to probe properties of the soil [30]. After discovering that the cosmic radiation is partially made up of neutrons, large networks of neutron monitor stations have been installed all over the globe [31, 32]. Following the conclusion by [33] that near-surface water was a significant influence factor for the epithermal cosmic-ray neutron flux, [34] found a qualitative relationship between snow water and neutrons below ground. In a discontinued follow-up study [35] using below-ground neutron detectors they could establish a qualitative relation between cosmic radiation and the water content of the soil. [36] proposed using albedo neutrons for soil water measurements in environmental sciences after space satellites found water on Mars [37, 38] and Moon [39, 40] using reflected cosmic-ray neutrons. Shortly after, motivated by experiments from [41], M. Zreda and D. Desilets approached this technique from a viewpoint of hydrology and particle physics, supported by Monte-Carlo simulations.

Their efforts to link cosmogenic neutron flux measurements with the soil water content showed success after several attempts and they established the field of cosmic-ray neutron sensing [42, 43]. The important steps in understanding the method are shown in Fig. 3. Three advances enabled the CRNS methodology: (1) Detector design: ^3He -based sensors with optimized polyethylene moderators and optionally cadmium shielding [44] prioritized epithermal neutrons, maximizing moisture sensitivity while minimizing unwanted contributions. (2) Footprint characterization: Simulations and field studies defined the horizontal (~ 100 m to 300 m) and vertical (~ 15 m to 80 cm) sensitivity [42], revealing depth-weighted and range-dependent spatial averaging [45]. As in most cases soil moisture is distributed inhomogeneously, an understanding of non-linear influences of irregular topologies was crucial for interpreting data from in-situ samples [46]. (3) Precise corrections: Air pressure effects (dominant) [47], air humidity [48], incoming radiation [49], vegetation [50] and soil composition [51] were systematically corrected for to isolate the soil moisture signal. The complex conditions for neutron scattering at the soil-air interface remained challenging, especially as the footprint expectations [52] could not be experimentally validated. The implementation of analytical descriptions of validated cosmic-ray neutron spectra by [53] and [54] marked a turning point as such allowed for straight forward calculations instead of the computationally inefficient and uncertain propagation of particles through kilometers of atmosphere. With the improved understanding of the footprint by Monte-Carlo simulations analytical functions could be derived accounting for various environmental parameters, yet under homogeneous conditions [55, 56]. After the energy-dependent detection characteristics for typical CRNS instruments was also understood [24] a more precise intensity relation could be found [57], which at the same time merged both previous hyperbolic and exponential descriptions [43, 50]. The development and release of the CRNS-specific and user-oriented Monte-Carlo tool URANOS [58] allowed a broader field of scientists to gain theoretical insights. Among them the understanding of the thermal neutron footprint [59], the interpretation of the snow water equivalent under patchy conditions [60] and the understanding of sub-footprint signal changes [61, 62]. Compared to other methods which measure soil moisture integrally beyond the point scale [7, 63], CRNS instruments were regarded as more straight-

forward and affordable. As such with the increasing success in yielding high precision several national networks decided for integration of CRPs in their program and for operationalizing the methodology.

2.2. Sensing Volume

The footprint of a CRNS detector covers the area and depth where the soil is probed and extends horizontally and vertically in the shape of an exponential function. This means that those parts close to the sensor and near the surface have a larger influence to the signal than others. The exponential shape might not follow the usual intuition for the sensitive range of an instrument, however, one might think of an analogy to hearing, where in a crowd sounds or speech in the vicinity can clearly be understood and everything far away becomes a constant background depending on the amount of people speaking. Thus, for the exponentially shaped footprint a quantile definition is applied to find a distance R within which most of the detected neutrons have probed the ground. The two- e -folding length equals to the 86 % quantile and the according footprint radius is denoted by R_{86} . Furthermore, the sensing volume itself depends on the actual moisture. The horizontal footprint ranges from around 220 m under dry conditions to 170 m for wet conditions and reduces to 130 m over water. The vertical penetration depth scales from 70 cm for dry to 20 cm for wet soils.

Due to the nature of the method, neutrons pass the soil-air interface several times and each scattering interaction disentangles origin and direction of the travel path. Applying shielding to any side of the CRP only partially blocks the flux from the respective direction, therefore the footprint can be shaped, but only to a certain amount, by instrument modifications [64]. The focus of this summary lies on the usual instruments which are equally sensitive to all directions.

2.2.1. Horizontal Footprint

A CRP detects neutrons isotropically in the radial direction, leading to the assumption of a circular footprint area, $A = \pi r^2$. Here, the travel distance r is defined as the length between the point of detection and the point of the neutron's first contact with the ground or its generation. As a result of multiple interactions, r depends on the neutron's initial energy and number of collisions and it can cover values between 0 m and 1000 m. Assuming a simple diffusion model of a point source one yields an exponentially decreasing intensity with travel distance, which legitimates the use of the two- e -folding length, i.e. the 86 % quantile Q_{86} , in order to define the footprint radius, where the footprint area then is $A = \pi R_{86}^2$. The horizontal weighting is carried out as follows:

$$W_r(r, h, \theta) \sim e^{-2r/R_{86}(h, \theta)}. \quad (1)$$

This definition only indirectly takes into account how often a neutron has probed the soil, therefore, the applicability is limited to cases of nearly homogeneous soil moisture conditions. On average a neutron probes the soil around three times until detection with the first interaction being the most dominant one.

This justifies the approach of using the first interaction with the soil. [62] quantifies the allowed deviations under heterogeneous soil moisture conditions.

The range distributions [56] can be described by exponential functions defining a near-field term below 50 m and a far-field term beyond:

$$I_0(h, \theta)W_r(h, \theta) = I_0 \cdot \begin{cases} (F_1 e^{-F_2 r} + F_3 e^{-F_4 r})(1 - e^{-F_0 r}) & 0 < r \leq 1 \\ F_1 e^{-F_2 r} + F_3 e^{-F_4 r} & 1 < r \leq 50 \\ F_5 e^{-F_6 r} + F_7 e^{-F_8 r} & 50 < r < 600 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

with r in m. I_0 represents the overall intensity and W_r denotes the radial weighting function. The parameters F_i represent either signal contributions or attenuation coefficients for a distance r . Alternatively, a rescaled distance $r^*(r, p, \theta)$ (see below) can be used, which can be considered as an unmodified distance r for standard environmental conditions. Each above defined interval contains one function modeling the main functional contributor, i.e. the soil moisture dependency, and one reflecting the second order correction. For ranges below 1 m a purely geometrical factor is added. This description holds for a detector layer being positioned at a height of 1–2 m. Parameter values are provided in Tab. A1 in [56].

The footprint changes with air pressure, e.g. increasing altitude of the sensor location [55]. A lower air density allows neutrons to cover longer distances between collisions. For example, the footprint can be 20 % larger at a ≈ 2000 m altitude (≈ 800 mbar) compared to sea level. The exponential dependence of the footprint weighting function is as follows:

$$W_r(h, \theta) \cdot f_p = W_r(h, \theta) \cdot \frac{0.5}{0.86 - \exp\left(-\frac{p}{p_0}\right)} = W_{r^*}(h, \theta) \text{ with } r^* = r \cdot \left(\frac{0.86 - \exp\left(-\frac{p}{p_0}\right)}{0.5}\right). \quad (3)$$

In good approximation the footprint scaling with air pressure can, however, be simplified to

$$W_r(h, \theta) \cdot f_p \approx W_r(h, \theta) \cdot \frac{p_0}{p}. \quad (4)$$

The footprint scaling factor f_{veg} for below-sensor biomass with height H_{veg} proposed by [55] and [56] based on neutron transport modeling is

$$W_r(h, \theta) \cdot f_{\text{veg}} = W_r(h, \theta) \cdot \left(1 - 0.17 \cdot \left(1 - e^{-0.41 H_{\text{veg}}}\right) \cdot \left(1 + e^{-7\theta}\right)\right), \quad (5)$$

where the vegetation height is H_{veg} in 4.4 kg/m² per m plant height. The influence to the footprint scaling of biomass above the sensor as in case of forests is still under evaluation.

An approximated weighting function W_r^* had been proposed in [56], which is an averaged estimation over dry and wet conditions:

$$I_0(h, \theta)W_r^* = I_0 \cdot \begin{cases} (30e^{-r^*/1.6} + e^{-r^*/100})(1 - e^{-3.7r^*}) & r^* \leq 1 \\ 30e^{-r^*/1.6} + e^{-r^*/100} & r^* > 1 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

with units for r^* in m.

Figure 4: Comparison of normalized horizontal weighting functions (a) from 0 m to 5 m, and (b) from 5 m to 300 m. Graphs show the previous almost exponential approach, in comparison to the revised, more detailed approach for three wetness conditions, and an approximation based on a simplified equation [56].

2.2.2. Vertical Footprint

Soil moisture below the surface is weighted with an exponentially decreasing function with the highest sensitivity to soil moisture changes in the upper layers. The vertical weighting function is constructed in an equal manner to the horizontal weighting function. Soil located more closely to the sensor are on average probed more deeply than remote parts of the footprint. The vertical weighting is described by

$$W_d(r, \theta) \sim e^{-2d/D_{86}(r, \theta)}. \quad (7)$$

The penetration depth D_{86} , is calculated as follows:

$$D_{86} = \frac{\text{g/cm}^2}{\rho_{\text{bulk}}} \left(p_0 + p_1 \left(p_2 + e^{-p_3 r^*} \right) \frac{p_4 + \theta}{p_5 + \theta} \right). \quad (8)$$

The quantity denotes up to which depth 86% of the detected neutrons had interactions in the soil. Numerical parameters are provided in Tab. A1 in [55]. D_{86} is rescaled by the soil bulk density ρ_{bulk} as less dense soils allow for a more deep penetration. As the unit of D_{86} is cm, the bulk density rescaling factor (in g/cm^3) is normalized through division by g/cm^2 . Equation (8) was originally calculated for a soil bulk density of 1.43 g/cm^3 and has been validated for heterogeneous topographies and significantly lower dense soils. Yet, for very low densities, below approximately 1 g/cm^3 , the accuracy is lower.

2.2.3. Thermal Footprint

The footprint scaling function \widetilde{W}_r for thermal neutrons [59] for a constant air humidity of 10 g/m^3 can be calculated as follows

$$\widetilde{W}_r(r, \theta) = r^{*F_1} \left(e^{-r^{*F_3} r^{*F_2}} + \frac{F_4}{r^*} \right)^{r^{*F_5} + F_6} \quad (9)$$

for $0 \text{ m} < r \leq 300 \text{ m}$. The penetration depth \widetilde{W}_d , is calculated as follows:

$$\widetilde{W}_d(d, \theta) = d^{F_7} \left(e^{-dF_9 d^{F_8}} + \frac{F_{10}}{d} \right)^{dF_{11} + F_{12}} \quad (10)$$

for $0 \text{ cm} < d \leq 150 \text{ cm}$. Parameter values for both thermal neutron equations are provided in Tab. A1 in [59].

2.3. Correction Factors

The cosmic-ray neutron spectrum results from a complex interplay between elementary particles, including leptons and baryons, which generate so-called atmospheric cascades or showers. Neutrons as a by-product of these processes make up a large part of the remaining radiation at ground level. When highly energetic, they interact with all matter, predominantly with hydrogen during moderation. The neutron density N_n at the ground then is influenced by various factors. Most involved processes exhibit a non-linear scaling. In order to derive a soil moisture value θ , there is a set of correction factors, which are partially based on simulations but mostly have been obtained empirically. The fully corrected neutron count rate of a sensor N_{corr} is calculated by

$$N_{\text{corr}} = N_n \cdot C_I \cdot C_p \cdot C_h \cdot C_{\text{veg}}, \quad (11)$$

where C_I denotes the incoming radiation correction, C_p the atmospheric pressure correction, C_h the air humidity correction and C_{veg} the correction for above-ground biomass.

The Neutron Monitor Data Base (NMDB)¹ provides real-time data about the incoming radiation I [65], which can be retrieved automatically. The established correction method uses then a standardized count rate for the respective detector I_{ref} for the incoming radiation correction

$$C_I = 1 + \gamma \left(\frac{I_{\text{ref}}}{I} - 1 \right), \quad (12)$$

using most often $\gamma = 1$. Alternatively, the scaling factor can be calculated by

$$\gamma = 1 - 0.075 (R_C - R_C^{\text{ref}}), \quad (13)$$

where R_C is the effective cutoff rigidity for the site and R_C^{ref} is the effective cutoff rigidity for the reference neutron monitor. [66] derived the following empirical relation

$$C_I = \left(\frac{I}{I_{\text{ref}}} \tau + 1 - \tau \right)^{-1}. \quad (14)$$

¹accessible via <http://www01.nmdb.eu/>

Here, τ is calculated from the atmospheric depth at the sensor location X , a location-dependent normalization factor K and ε - a correction factor that adjusts the sensitivity of the standard lead neutron monitor to that of a CRP, assumed to be $\varepsilon = 1$:

$$\tau(X, R_c) = \varepsilon \cdot K (-c_0 X + c_1) \cdot \left(1 - \exp\left(- (c_2 X + c_3) R_c^{c_4 X - c_5}\right)\right), \quad (15)$$

The parameters are found in Tab. 1 in [66].

The incoming radiation including the secondary particles are attenuated by the atmosphere. The reference air pressure p at the sensor location provides a good estimator for the mass of the air column. The barometric pressure correction therefore can be written using the atmospheric depth at reference pressure $X_{\text{ref}} \approx 1000 \text{ g/cm}^2$ as

$$C_p = \exp\left(\frac{X - X_{\text{ref}}}{\lambda_{\text{atm}}}\right), \quad (16)$$

with the atmospheric attenuation length λ_{atm} . In general $\lambda_{\text{atm}} = 132 \text{ g/cm}^2$ is assumed [47]. Yet, this parameter itself depends on energy range, altitude and cutoff rigidity as it represents an average of interaction lengths of different primary and secondary air shower particles. Literature values of measurements range from (130–165) g/cm^2 , overviews can be found in [49], [67] or [68].

The following correction function is used for air humidity [48]:

$$C_h = 1 + \alpha_{\text{hum}} (h_{\text{abs}} - h_{\text{abs}}^{\text{ref}}), \quad (17)$$

with $\alpha_{\text{hum}} = 0.0054 \text{ m}^3/\text{g}$, absolute humidity h_{abs} and an arbitrary reference value of for example $h_{\text{abs}}^{\text{ref}} = 12 \text{ g/m}^3$, which corresponds to 50 % relative humidity at 25°C. With the reference humidity at ground level, a skyward exponentially decreasing air humidity is assumed using an attenuation length of 2300 m. For thermal neutrons the humidity correction factor $\alpha_{\text{hum}} = 0.0021 \text{ m}^3/\text{g}$ had been proposed [69].

For the biomass above the ground but below the sensor a simple relation based on empirical data was proposed by [70]:

$$C_{\text{veg}} = \frac{1}{1 - 0.009 \cdot \text{AGB}}, \quad (18)$$

according to which epithermal neutron count rates are reduced by 0.9 % for every kg of dry above-ground biomass per m^2 (AGB). This influence is similar to the reduction of 1 % per kg/m^2 reported by [71] and confirmed by [72], yet with significant variations among sites. Additionally, based on neutron transport modelling of forest topologies, [73] qualitatively found significant non-linear effects from the tree canopy.

[74] proposed for biomass estimation to take into account the epithermal-to-thermal count ratio N_R by

$$C_{\text{veg}} = 1 - b \cdot \text{AGB} + c \cdot N_R, \quad (19)$$

with to be determined parameters b and c . For the linear correction relation [75] suggested to only use the epithermal-to-

thermal ratio or only the thermal neutron flux N_T with a site specific parameter k to describe effects of biomass:

$$C_{\text{veg}} = 1 - k \cdot N_T. \quad (20)$$

[76] and [77] expanded the procedure. Their results favored to use the thermal neutron channel. The current available literature provides ambiguous results with respect to this methodology. For the precise accounting of biomass it remains, however, an open question as to which extent a simple linear reduction of intensity may apply and how site- or plant-specific considerations need to be accounted for.

2.4. Soil Moisture Determination

The above-ground neutron spectrum contains two parts. The pure incoming radiation Φ_{inc} never had any contact with soil. The albedo component Φ_{alb} is then defined as those neutrons which passed the soil-air interface at least once:

$$\Phi_{\text{tot}} = \Phi_{\text{inc}} + \Phi_{\text{alb}} \rightarrow N = k_{\text{inc}} N_0 + k_{\text{alb}}(\theta) N_0. \quad (21)$$

Soil moisture θ is then inferred from the intensity change of the reflected component. As any hydrogen in the environment contributes to the signal, all water pools have to be added up, including biomass θ_{org} and chemically bound lattice water θ_{lw} , which is typically in the order of (1–2) % volumetric soil moisture:

$$\theta = \theta_{\text{mob}} + \theta_{\text{org}} + \theta_{\text{lw}}. \quad (22)$$

Although the typical definitions of soil moisture account only for the available water θ_{mob} , this work for reasons of simplicity implicitly assumes the extension of this term by including hydrogen contributions, which can be converted to an integrated effective soil moisture according to $\theta = \sum_i \theta_i$.

The count rate of the sensor N is assumed to be derived from a reference parameter N_0 , which is supposed to be the instrument count rate over entirely dry soil.

To the current date, four intensity scaling functions have been published. The hyperbolic N0 method, the exponential COSMIC operator and the Universal Calibration Function (UCF) and the Universal Transport Solution (UTS) with a combination of exponential and hyperbolic terms. The first two models made general assumptions and claimed the detector to be sensitive only the epithermal range of 10 eV to 100 keV. UCF considered partial contributions of thermal neutrons. UTS was the first model which included the actual instrumental response function.

2.4.1. N0 Method

The first proposed function to translate neutron flux changes to gravimetric or volumetric soil moisture θ follows a simple hyperbola

$$\theta(N) = \frac{a_0}{\frac{N}{N_0} - a_1} - a_2, \quad (23)$$

with the parameters $a_0 = 0.0808$, $a_1 = 0.372$ and $a_2 = 0.115$, derived from an empirical analysis in [43]. a_1 equals the incoming radiation fraction k_{inc} , a_0 and a_2 have the units of m^3/m^3

or kg/kg and N_0 is the intrinsic detector count rate parameter. Its comparably easy mathematical form and own commercial activities of the authors led to a widespread use. The approach to recalibrate the sensor to individual site conditions lead in many cases to satisfying results, therefore, authors claimed the feasibility of the equation by using slightly different sets of a_i parameters or adjusted N_0 values. This, however, questioned the validity of the CRNS method in general. As seen in Fig. 5 the hyperbolic expression can be adapted to either drier or wetter conditions by changing the parameters, but not to both moisture ranges at the same time. In fact in most wet situations above 10 % soil moisture the slope of the hyperbola nearly follows the expectation. It has been shown later by [57] that the N0 equation is also overdefined by one parameter. Therefore, adaptations of the parameters in the equation are not unique.

2.4.2. UCF and COSMIC Method

Both methods describe $\theta(N)$ as an exponential function. UCF [46] models the above-ground neutron intensity with the following equation, which uses the count rate over water N_S as a reference.

$$\frac{N}{N_S} = 4.486 e^{-48.1 \cdot \text{hmf}} + 4.195 e^{-6.181 \cdot \text{hmf}}. \quad (24)$$

The hydrogen mole fraction, hmf (mol/mol), is defined as:

$$\text{hmf} = \frac{\sum_i H_i}{\sum_i A_i},$$

where $\sum_i H_i = H_\tau + H_{\text{SOC}} + H_\theta + H_{\text{AGB}}.$ (25)

The sum of hydrogen moles $\sum H_i$ is calculated from lattice water (H_τ), soil organic carbon lattice water equivalent (H_{SOC}), pore water (H_θ) and vegetation (H_{AGB}) inside the support volume. Similarly,

$$\sum_i A_i = \text{NO} + \text{SiO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}_\tau + \text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{SOC}} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_\theta + \text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5 + \text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{AGB}} \quad (26)$$

is the sum of all amounts of air (NO), soil (SiO_2), lattice water (H_2O_τ), soil organic carbon lattice water equivalent ($\text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{SOC}}$), pore water ($\text{H}_2\text{O}_\theta$), and above-ground biomass ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5 + \text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{AGB}}$) inside the support volume. For a homogeneous SiO_2 soil one would obtain $\text{hmf}(\theta) = 1.556 / (1 + 2.334 \theta)$ for θ in m^3 / m^3 .

Although mathematically incorrect and physically inadequate with focusing only on onedimensional transport, the COSMIC operator by [78] had been applied in various studies. It combines the representations of the three physical processes (High-energy neutron attenuation in the soil, evaporation and attenuation of evaporation neutrons) leading to a one-dimensional calculation of the fast neutron flux. The analytic function for N_{COSMOS} , the number of fast neutrons reaching the CRP at a near-surface measurement point, is:

$$N_{\text{COSMOS}} = N \int_0^\infty A(z) [\alpha \rho_s(z) + \rho_w(z)] \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{m_s(z)}{L_1} - \frac{m_w(z)}{L_2}\right) dz, \quad (27)$$

where N is a constant, $A(z)$ is a function of depth z , α is a constant, and $\rho_s(z)$, $\rho_w(z)$, $m_s(z)$, and $m_w(z)$ are functions of depth as well, representing the physical properties of the soil and water at different depths. L_1 and L_2 are constants related to the transport lengths for soil and water, respectively, and need to be calibrated according to the site conditions or with neutron transport models.

2.4.3. UTS Method

The *Universal Transport Solution* (UTS) combined the previous exponential and hyperbolic approaches into one form [57]. Therefore, it is well matched for dry and wet soil conditions. The UTS intensity relation for volumetric or gravimetric soil moisture is:

$$I(\theta, h) = N_D \left(\frac{p_1 + p_2 \theta}{p_1 + \theta} (p_0 + p_6 h + p_7 h^2) + e^{-p_3 \theta} (p_4 + p_5 h) \right). \quad (28)$$

The UTS function is a general description of $I(\theta, h)$ and does not require a separate air humidity correction. The included water vapor scaling is in most cases in agreement with [48]. The parameters p_i are derived from a two-dimensional fit on simulated data sets of full-scale cosmic air showers, see also Tab. A1 in [57]. The factor N_D accounts for the average specific detector count rate and can be determined with any combination of I , θ and h . For soil moisture retrieval $\theta(I, h)$ has to be inverted numerically. The 'MCNP drf' parameter sets are appropriate for most detectors. UTS was calculated for a reference bulk density of 1.43 g/cm^3 .

An approximation for the inverted UTS equation for volumetric soil moisture is

$$\theta(I_N, h) = (0.0248 (I_N)^{-6.31} + 86.8 e^{-4.516 I_N}). \quad (29)$$

with the scaled, corrected and normalized intensity

$$I_N = \frac{I}{I_D} C_h^U. \quad (30)$$

I_D serves in a similar function as the normalization factor for the intrinsic count rate N_D . It normalizes the measured intensity I to I_N for Eq. (29) to values between 0 and 1. Volumetric soil moisture is in units of $100 \cdot \text{m}^3 / \text{m}^3$ for a reference bulk density of 1.43 g/cm^3 . The humidity correction

$$C_h^U = 1 + 6.93 \cdot 10^{-3} h - 2.4 \cdot 10^{-5} h^2 \quad (31)$$

with absolute humidity h in g/m^3 is independent of the intensity

Figure 5: CRN intensity scaling for a range of soil moisture values, normalized to 10%. Compared are the N0 method, the COSMIC forward operator, UCF and the UTS method to a full-scale MCNP simulation of a CRP (CRS-1000 by Hydroinnova). The soil bulk density is 1.43 g/m^3 . Modified from [57].

scaling and derived from the UTS equation. It is also possible to use C_h from Eq. (17).

2.4.4. On-site Calibration and Soil Sampling

For soil moisture retrieval using the $\theta(I)$ -relation cosmic-ray instruments require a calibration by obtaining the soil bulk density and soil moisture at a given point. Typically, soil samples are collected and then analyzed via oven drying. Original strategies involved horizontal equal averaging of the calibration data, for example [45] utilized a sampling strategy based on computations by [42] to provide each sample a uniform weight. The sampling positions at 25 m, 75 m, and 200 m were supposed to align with a nearly exponential weighting function. [79] first conducted this horizontal weighting with an irregularly distributed sensor network. The original COSMOS sampling method was based on inferior neutron simulations [52] that had been revised [55], specifically the assumption of a constant footprint size. The updated sampling strategy, see Fig. 6, involves taking samples at different distances from the sensor at different depths and then apply the horizontal and vertical weighting functions to calculate a soil moisture value averaged according to the sensitivity of a CRNS instrument.

The procedure is as follows:

- Obtain soil samples at representative points within the sensor's footprint at in at least three representative depths each. One extraction point shall lie in the direct vicinity of the sensor, then select points in the near-field within the first 50 m and far field beyond. At each sample at least at 5 cm, 15 cm and deeper.
- Use the horizontal and vertical weighting functions to determine the weights w_i of samples. Due to the variable footprint, make a first order estimation of the average soil moisture of the largest part of volume within the sensor's sensitivity range.

Figure 6: (a) Illustration of regions of equal contribution (20% quantiles) to the neutron signal for three climates (humidity 2, 7 and 20 g/m^3 , soil moisture 2, 20 and 50 Vol-% .) (b) The COSMOS standard sampling scheme, compared to two exemplary three-radii schemes based on the revised weighting function for dry ($h = 1 \text{ g/m}^3$, $\theta = 1 \text{ %}$) and wet ($h = 10 \text{ g/m}^3$, $\theta = 40 \text{ %}$) conditions. Circles represent the borders of the 33% quantiles (grey, dashed), and arbitrary sampling points on the annuluses (colored, solid). [56]

At each point obtain the (vertical) weights w_i^d of the different depths by using Eq. (7) and (8). Then calculate the weighted average of them by $\bar{\theta}^d = \sum_i \theta_i w_i^d / \sum_i w_i^d$. Then, obtain the (horizontal) weights w_i of the vertically weighted soil moisture samples at the respective radii of the points using Eq. (2), (4) and (5) or alternatively (6). Then calculate the weighted average of them by $\bar{\theta} = \sum_i \bar{\theta}_i^d w_i / \sum_i w_i$.

- Use the intensity relation in Sec. 2.4, for example Eq. (30) and (29), with the averaged $\bar{\theta}$ in order to determine the intrinsic detector count rate parameter.

2.5. State-of-the-Art Devices

The sensor is usually mounted 1–2 m above the ground surface and equipped with two units - one bare detector for determining the thermal neutron flux and one counter enclosed by a neutron moderator of approximately 25 mm polyethylene. This makes the system most suited for rate changes in the epithermal-to-fast neutron energy range. The energy sensitivity of the detector, the so-called response function, extends, however, into the thermal as well as the fast neutron domain. Therefore, the moderated detector is partly sensitive to high energy neutrons, which for example leads to the 'road effect' [80]. The thermal neutron contamination constitutes up to 20% of the CRP signal [24]. Both non-epithermal neutron ranges exhibit a different and much smaller dependence on the environmental hydrogen content than epithermal-to-fast neutrons. In addition, the thermal (bare) neutron detector can have partial contribution from epithermal/fast neutrons in the same order [81].

The common neutron detector types used in CRNS are:

- Gaseous counters with the neutron converter being the counting gas itself (helium-3),

Figure 7: (left) Response functions of a bare neutron counter and detectors embedded in moderators of thicknesses 20–27.5 mm in steps of 2.5 mm. All models except for one of the 25 mm versions are equipped with a thermal neutron shield. In order to compare energy ranges a cosmic-ray neutron spectrum above the soil at 20 % soil moisture and 15 g/m³ air humidity is drawn. The sensitivity to hydrogen according to Fig. 2 is shown by the shaded blue filling. (right): Weighting of this neutron spectrum with the response functions shows the total count rate contribution of the different energy domains. Here, the curve of the bare counter is decreased by a factor of four. [82]

- Gaseous counters with the neutron converter (boron trifluoride, ¹⁰BF₃) in a mixture with a counting gas,
- Gaseous counters with the neutron converter as a solid material (boron-10-lined or lithium-6 metal),
- Lithium-6-loaded scintillators with optical readout.

The characteristics regarding the signal response to soil moisture in the viewpoint of CRNS does not depend on the converter itself but on the moderator design. The moderator can be modified to partially but mostly insufficiently block neutrons from undesired directions, however, at the cost of loss of counting statistics [83]. Similarly, surrounding the top part of an CRNS instrument by large moderator blocks can confine the footprint to the very vicinity of the detector [84].

Figure 8: Schematic pulse height spectra of helium-3 (blue), lithium-6 (yellow), boron-10-trifluoride (green) and boron-10-lined (orange) including background (dashed).

Only a few isotopes exhibit thermal neutron absorption cross sections high enough and their reaction products (charged particles) have *Q* values large enough to be separated from background and other processes. There are ³He, ⁶Li and ¹⁰B. The scarcity of helium-3 requires the adoption of more cost efficient solutions [85, 86, 87]. The following table summarizes the common neutron converters and their primary reaction channels.

2.5.1. Helium-3

Helium-3 has the advantage that it acts as a neutron converter as well as a counting gas. By absorbing a neutron the total reaction energy of 764 keV is distributed to both conversion products, a hydrogen (573 keV) and a triton ion (191 keV)

CO	Reaction	CS
³ He	³ He+n → ³ H+p + 0.764 MeV	5327
⁶ Li	⁶ Li+n → ³ H+α + 4.78 MeV	940
¹⁰ B	¹⁰ B+n → ⁷ Li+α + 2.79 MeV (6.4 %)	3837
	¹⁰ B+n → ⁷ Li+γ + α + 2.31 MeV (93.6 %)	

Table 1: Common neutron converters (CO) and their primary reaction channels with the cross section CS at 25.2 meV in barn.

Figure 9: Schematic of a helium-3 tube (left) and pulse height spectrum (right). The neutron is converted into a proton and a triton ion, which are emitted back-to-back. The primary ionization electrons drift towards the central anode with gas amplification near the wire. The pulse height spectrum is comprised of the full ionization peak and a plateau region of partial energy deposition due to wall effects. [88]

emitted back-to-back. Low-*Z* elements have a small stopping power for charged particles. A partial signal loss by one of the reaction products colliding with the cathode is probable. This is called wall effect and can be identified in the spectrum as edges at the minimum energy possible. In order to reduce the track length a so-called buffer can be added, a higher-*Z* noble gas like krypton, which increases the stopping power but is transparent for neutrons. Typically, wall effect contributions of up to 20 % are accepted. Fig. 9 shows the sketch of a helium-3 proportional counter and the pulse height reaction product spectrum shape obtained with such a device [89]. Additionally, at the lower end there is a continuum of background events by photons. It scales by the relative γ abundance and the volume to surface ratio of the device, as the main contribution are wall interactions. Helium-3 tubes can be operated with a distinct lower threshold as the

spectrum does not extend significantly below 190 keV, which lies well above the gamma background. The original COSMOS instruments [51] and most of the roving systems [80] are based on helium-3.

2.5.2. Boron Trifluoride

Boron trifluoride acts as a neutron converter, however it is not a counting gas, it is a so-called quencher [90]. Charge amplification occurs efficiently in noble gases, where collisions with gas atoms directly can eject electrons. More complex molecules have rotational and vibrational degrees of freedom, to which the collision energy can be transferred to instead of yielding charge multiplication. Boron trifluoride therefore requires approximately an equal amount of counting gas in combination to uphold the gas gain. Yet, this limits the total absorption efficiency, which is typically lower compared to helium-3 [91, 92]. On the other hand, BF_3 tubes are less susceptible to temperature changes than helium-3 tubes [93]. Currently, BF_3 is the main alternative to the costly helium-3, however, its toxicity and considerably high costs prevents a more widespread adoption.

2.5.3. Boron-lined

Boron-lined detectors feature a micrometer-thick coating of boron or boron carbide (B_4C) applied to the inner surface of the tube wall. This conversion layer must be thin so that the reaction products can escape the material and enter the counting gas, where they can be detected [94]. As counting gases typical mixtures like $\text{Ar}:\text{CO}_2$ are used [95]. Compared to gaseous converters, a key disadvantage of boron-lined detectors is the continuous energy spectrum they produce, see Fig. 8. This occurs because only a portion of the particle track lies within the gas, reducing the completeness of the detected signal. The resulting continuous spectrum necessitates an unavoidable low-energy cutoff, which not only lowers detection efficiency but also makes the system more sensitive to gain fluctuations or threshold drifts [82]. Such variations can unpredictably affect the counting rate. Therefore, boron-lined detectors have more stringent requirements on frontend electronics in terms of stability and signal-to-noise characteristics. The lack of conversion efficiency can be compensated for example by multi-tube arrangements [96].

2.5.4. Lithium

Lithium metal converter layers can extend to 50 micrometers or more due to the lower stopping power of lithium for charged particle tracks and the larger kinetic energy of the signal ions. As a result, lithium-6-based detectors can achieve a higher detection efficiency than boron-lined models, but still lower than helium-3 tubes. Lithium metal reacts easily exothermic upon contact with water or air humidity, which requires special precautions for their production. Due to the comparably high kinetic energy of the conversion products in most detectors the pulse height spectrum is cut geometrically, leading to a 'wedge' shape resembling $1/\cos(E)$ at the upper end, see Fig. 8. For CRNS a growing number of sites is equipped with this type of instruments [97, 98, 99]

2.5.5. Further Remarks on Gaseous Detectors

Relevant for low count rate applications is the contamination of the tube material by α -emitters [100], which can be, dependent on the composition, in the order of $10^{-4}\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. Radioisotopes, specifically such as α -emitters, can mimic neutron signals which are often indistinguishable from neutron conversion tracks: These radioisotopes create a continuous spectrum of deposited energies up to several MeV and one part of it inevitably lies below the signal region [101]. Using a standard alloy for the tube housing with usual radioisotope abundances can lead to a background signal of up to 1/3 of the total events. Methods to suppress these contributions are adopting high-purity materials or applying a coating of such to the inside of the cylinder mantle.

2.5.6. Scintillators

Scintillators are materials which emit light if a charged particle passes through. There is a wide range of detector types and processes: gaseous scintillation, liquid scintillation, scintillating fibres, scintillating plates as organic or inorganic compounds. They all share that they are partially transparent for the scintillation light they produce but vary in emission wavelength, afterglow, temperature stability, gamma sensitivity and costs [102].

A typical neutron scintillation detector requires a neutron converter, a scintillator, a lightguide, optionally a wavelength shifter, and a photosensitive element [103]. Except for gaseous scintillation [104] the neutron converter must be embedded in the scintillator matrix. Any of the mentioned materials can be used. There are two strategies possible: either using a large bulk scintillator with at a rather low concentration of absorber, most often lithium fluoride (LiF), or a scintillator which is much less transparent, commonly zinc sulfide ($\text{ZnS}(\text{Ag})$) highly loaded with a converter, and apply it as a thin coating. Other neutron converters like boron nitride can be applied in this context as well [105]. Firstly, the size of such a scintillator is limited, becoming intransparent for higher concentrations of converter, leading to scintillator plates and wavelength-shifters being sandwiched [106, 107]. Wavelength-shifting materials are used to channel out the produced light by converting it to a different frequency [108]. As a result, the Bragg condition of the materials with different optical refraction index allows the photons to be transported by internal reflection to either end. Here, an optical element focuses the light on a photodetector. This can either be a (classical) photomultiplier or much smaller silicon photomultiplier. The former requires a high voltage supply and is sensitive to temperature and magnetic field influences and the latter is significantly less efficient and its noise strongly depends on the temperature. A loaded scintillator is not only sensitive to neutrons, it will also create signals for muons, gammas or electrons passing through [109]. An identification of the sources of the signals is not directly possible. For these scintillator detectors the spectrum of the recorded light output is typically largely smeared out, however, the pulse rise time can be used to identify different types of signal origins. Additionally it has to be noted, that contrary to gaseous detectors plastic scintillators contain hydrogen and therefore act as moderator themselves.

2.6. CRNS Networks

The expansion of single stationary cosmic-ray neutron instruments into large-scale networks has significantly advanced hydrological monitoring and by the large-scale availability of representative CRNS datasets such networks meanwhile can serve as ground-truthing for remote sensing products [110, 111, 112]. The COSMOS initiative [51] pioneered continental-scale soil moisture observations in the USA and beyond. With its originally planned 50 sensors it demonstrated the potential of the method for environmental studies and in terms of reliability. With discontinued funding after ten years the remaining detectors were commercialized.

Figure 10: Locations of the European sites with CRNS installations (the symbols show the climatic zone to which they belong) as well as sites, which are currently under construction. [113]

Following this first instrument pool, COSMOS-UK [114] established a high-resolution network across the United Kingdom, integrating around 50 sensors within their hydrometeorological measurements program. The CosmOz project in Australia deployed 18 instruments [115]. Smaller-scaled networks were established in India [116, 117] and Ireland [118]. In Germany, the ADAPTER project [119] further extends CRNS applications in agricultural contexts by combining real-time neutron data with weather forecasting models [120]. Most recently, the

Brandenburg Cluster [121] in Germany was set up, focusing on improving agricultural water management through selectively placed CRNS stations. These networks highlight CRNS as a tool for bridging ground-based and remote sensing measurements or catchment hydrology [122]. An overview of stations in Europe is provided in Fig. 10.

2.7. Simulation Tools

Neutron transport models are essential to better understand and advance the CRNS technique. The main tools to understand signal influences are MCNP [123] with the Cosmic Source option [124] and URANOS [58] with the Cosmic-Ray spectrum from [125] and [54].

Figure 11: (a) Aerial view of an urban test site. (b) Abstract model of the area using geometric shapes and colour-coded material definitions. (c) URANOS simulation of epithermal neutron flux in a detector layer above the surface. Modified from [126]

Geant4 is currently rarely used [26]. MCNP requires a licensing procedure due to its dual-use potential and demands a more in-depth study of steering-file configurations from the user, but it can model all types of particles which are associated in the neutron production and their interplay. URANOS is provided as Open Source and relies on a graphical user interface and several features which are tailored towards Cosmic-Ray Neutron sensing like built-in detector response functions. Another beneficial functionality of its engine is that URANOS can be fed directly with complex topographies which are extruded as three-dimensional pixels (voxels). That allows to model even complex terrain like shown in Fig. 11. CRNS as a transdisciplinary method highly benefits from the expertise of nuclear and particle physics. Therefore, the underlying physics and processes are very well understood. Results from such simulation tools are very accurate, however, all such setups require simplifications of the actual topography. As to such the obtained results do not

need to be questioned on the validity of the model, but on to which extend the virtual domain with its features is representative for the measurements and conditions in the field. Thus, the last decade had seen a continuous refinement of procedures and methods for CRNS.

2.8. Software tools for CRNS data processing

Raw neutron counts from CRNS instruments require a longer sequence of correction, calibration and quality-control steps before the soil water content as an observable is retrieved. Differences in how air pressure, incoming neutron flux, atmospheric water vapor, biomass and other hydrogen pools are treated have led to diverging processing pipelines across networks, which hampers cross-site comparison and the creation of harmonised data products. In recent years, several open-source Python tools have been developed to address this gap and to make best-practice workflows more accessible to the community, specifically they take over the treatment of the more complex mathematical equations, for example for weighting calibration samples. The following tools form an emerging software ecosystem around CRNS that lowers the entry barrier for new users and supports reproducible data analysis by providing transparent and shareable implementations of the usually recommended processing workflows.

CRNP_y (Cosmic-Ray Neutron Python library) has been introduced as a rather lightweight, instrument-agnostic toolbox that supports both stationary and roving probes, including routines for atmospheric, biomass and road corrections, footprint estimation, uncertainty quantification and depth extrapolation, as well as Jupyter-based tutorials [127]. The *crspy* package (Cosmic-Ray neutron Sensor PYTHON tool) offers similarly a comprehensive, configuration-driven pipeline that implements the usual correction factors, site metadata handling and calibration procedures for stationary sensors [128]. The CORN_ish series [129, 130] is the CRNS processing and analysis framework with the longest legacy, providing modular routines for importing, correcting and visualising CRNS time series, with a particular emphasis on roving and near-real-time data handling.

2.9. Specific Applications

For CRNS there are three typical modes of operation to sense environmental water: Stationary operation, mobile surveys with sensors on vehicles and buried detectors for snow-water equivalent measurements. Currently, the method is still extended into serving other hydrological applications which for example necessitate a deeper sensing volume based on the down-hole technique [131].

2.9.1. Stationary Measurements

The main purpose of most CRNS installations is producing a consistent time series of measurements. This approach is used for the detection of temporal patterns, such as seasonal variations, rainfall infiltration, and irrigation events, providing data for hydrological research, water management and climate monitoring. Two examples of such time series are shown in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13.

Figure 12: Example of a time series from an agricultural site in West Germany showing a) precipitation, b) Neutron Count Rate, c) volumetric soil moisture estimated from CRNS (black) and reference (blue) from the averaging of the SoilNet sensors, and d) crop rotation. The yellow areas indicate vegetated periods and the red dashed line shows the HUMAX calibration window. Modified from [132].

Figure 13: Example of a time series of a wet site on the Eastern Tibetan Plateau with organic soils. Comparison of weighted in situ measurements including the equivalent water of soil organic carbon (SOC) in comparison to retrieved volumetric soil moisture from CRNS (UTS and NO) and the full-scale Monte Carlo simulation (URANOS). The deviations of each of the methods are given compared to weighted in situ measurements (blue). All data are smoothed by a 24-h rolling mean. Modified from [133].

Both undertake the effort to illustrate that CRNS yields very representative soil water estimates. If the site and the conditions are very well understood on the scale of the footprint corrections and influences can be determined properly. If parts of the time-series do not match expectations, like in both cases towards the end of the data taking, it is in most cases due other influences which are captured by the instrument. Currently, for the method overall a precision of around 5 % volumetric soil moisture can

be assumed.

2.9.2. Mobile Measurements

While stationary CRNS allows one to obtain the hourly variability of soil moisture within a static footprint, mobile applications intend to measure the spatial variability of environmental water across larger areas or along large transects. The so-called method of roving uses the same detection principle as the stationary CRNS but deploys multiple and larger neutron detectors in order to achieve higher count rates at much shorter recording periods [82]. Roving applications extend the CRNS footprint beyond the possibilities of collocating instruments [134, 135]. It allows for a coverage from the field scale to catchments and basins up to mesoscale assessments of soil moisture [136, 137, 138, 71, 139, 80, 140, 141, 142, 143, 144, 145, 146]. One example of a roving campaign is shown in Fig. 14.

Figure 14: Mobile volumetric soil moisture measurement by the CRNS rover in an agricultural field. Data were interpolated from points (black cross) which represent the path driven by the rover within one minute of acquisition time. Actual hydrological features like a creek in the valley and dry hilltops are evident, but other local influences like roads affect the derived soil moisture likewise. [80]

2.9.3. Snow Water Equivalent

As neutrons are sensitive to all sources of hydrogen in the environment, a CRP can also be used to measure snow. This has been carried using neutron detectors installed above the ground as well as below the snow cover.

For Cosmic-Ray Neutron sensors installed above soil and snow, the signal is strongly influenced by the water or ice layer. The dynamic range of snow water equivalent (SWE) extends to approximately 300 mm, yet for reasonably low uncertainties to 100 mm to 150 mm. Influence factors are the fact that snow cover is often patchy and the soil moisture under the snow pack as the method is unable to distinguish between both water bodies. Most studies were supported by neutron transport modeling since early on [147]. For above-ground installations, the inherently heterogeneous distribution of snow impedes a straight forward validation [148], yet empirically good correlations were found [149]. After finding non-linear relationships for the intensity for melting and accumulation phase [150], [60] showed in LIDAR-supported Monte-Carlo simulations based on URANOS that CRNS is capable of sensing the correct amount of snow water equivalent even under patchy conditions. [151] confirmed the general validity of the conversion approaches, however, a generalized model is not yet published.

Another common neutron measurement application involves the installation below the snow surface [152]. However, besides numerous advantages this approach significantly reduces the measurement footprint to $\sim 1 - 2 \text{ m}^2$ due to the neutron attenuation length in snow [153]. [154] suggested, assuming that the neutron attenuation by water ($\Lambda = 4.8 \text{ cm}$) is linear,

$$\text{SWE} = -\Lambda \ln \left(\frac{N - N_{\text{snow}}}{N_{\text{SWC}} - N_{\text{snow}}} \right) \quad (32)$$

with the intensity above the snow cover $N_{\text{snow}} = 0.24 \cdot N_0$ and the intensity above ground without snow N_{SWC} at the respective soil moisture.

2.10. Status and Open Questions

CRNS provides a precise non-invasive method for soil moisture monitoring but requires a holistic consideration of detector characteristics, environmental corrections and validation of modeling approaches to yields its full potential. Ongoing systematic benchmarking and uncertainty quantification are still essential research goals for improving the measurement principle. The following summarizes and evaluates the current open methodological questions in CRNS.

2.10.1. Signal Generation and Neutron Propagation

Monte-Carlo tools like URANOS and MCNP are physically well suited to model neutron propagation. Such have been employed successfully in a large number of contexts [67, 47, 42, 43, 45, 52, 48, 147, 46, 50, 55, 155, 12, 56, 126, 80, 24, 156, 60, 73, 82, 84, 57, 64, 59, 157, 83, 61, 62, 158, 131, 159, 69, 160, 133, 161, 132, 162, 148]. While most of the studies in the early period relied on MCNPX [163] and later MCNP6 [123] the more recent results were mostly obtained using URANOS [58]. Systematic benchmarks and comparisons are required to determine the extent to which these models represent real-world scenarios. The CRNS methodology, however, is faced with a circular dependency: the accuracy of neutron transport simulations, essential for signal corrections and estimates, relies on empirical validation against field measurements. Yet, these measurements themselves require prior simulation-derived corrections to isolate the true soil moisture signal. This interdependence often introduces a self-referential uncertainty loop, necessitating iterative benchmarking, data-driven validations and synthetic experiments for rigorous validation. To validate intensity relation models one needs to apply to in-situ measurements vertical and horizontal weighting functions which can only be extracted from simulations. In order to have these measurements serve as ground truth they need to be converted or scaled to CRNS intensities, yet, the procedures are based on the same first principles models they shall verify. Specifically in the earlier simulations the cosmic-ray neutron spectra were not accurate, mostly due to the limitations of MCNPX, and oversimplified detection models were used. With MCNP6 and the work of Sato in 2015 [125] integrated directly into URANOS, simulation results became much more realistic and reliable.

2.10.2. Footprint and Topological Inhomogeneities

The current footprint weighting functions, which depend on soil moisture and air humidity, have been derived from homogeneous simulations [56]. Studies have shown that to some extent small deviations in the topography and soil moisture distribution are still covered by the horizontal weighting [126, 62]. The vertical weighting functions showed very robust performance even in cases of inhomogeneous soil [133]. There are, however, limitations as horizontally shown for sub-footprint fields with irrigation [158] or vertically in cases of snow above rocks [60]. The delineations, if possible, have not yet been worked out. The footprint definitions for CRNS relied on the point of first soil contact [55] or thermalization point [59], however, neutrons cross the soil-atmosphere interface several times. As far as the initial interaction is the most dominant, the correct attribution of further soil probing points is still lacking.

Typically, the location of the sensor is chosen such that its footprint covers a representative area of the landscape that is monitored. However, the strong effect of the near-field on the signal has to be considered and sensor placement close to large hydrogen pools such as ponds or buildings should be avoided. Moreover, the signal is also influenced by the detector's height above the soil showing a stronger effect of the near field and a smaller overall horizontal footprint size as the detector approaches the ground. Typically, an installation at a height of half a metre above soil is considered acceptable, although higher installations are preferred. That is especially the case for the application of SWE monitoring in which the effective detector height above ground changes by increasing snow cover thickness [153] or agricultural installations in case the vegetation height approaches the sensor [132].

As far as shallow hillslopes do not influence the CRNS signal, mountains and topographies with large height variations significantly influence the signal as for example had been shown by [161]. Although such environments as presented in the simulations are too extreme, due to the large footprint alpine or prealpine sites can easily fall in such categories. For such, still a framework and understanding of signal influences needs to be worked out. For mobile measurements such inhomogeneities are regularly encountered as the road on which the sensor is driven usually exhibits a different effective moisture content as the surrounding. [80] worked out correction functions for several types and widths of roads, however, an analytical description for such significant near-field influences has not yet been presented.

2.10.3. Count Rate to Soil Moisture Conversion

Spatially and temporally variable factors within the footprint influencing the neutron signal have often been identified as the source of unexplained features in the data. These discoveries sometimes led to new scientific insights on neutron transport and even led to improved models in subsequent works [79, 150, 74, 64, 148]. However, at most heterogeneous sites CRNS calibration and validation poses a major challenge, as the support volume can only be probed and understood partially and the influence of the patches in the footprint to the signal is usually not known precisely enough [164, 165, 166]. For this reason, voluntarily or involuntarily, many authors have reported

differing shapes of the neutron–moisture curve and have conducted site-specific empirical parameterizations of the N0 function [43] to fit their data [167, 168, 169, 170, 73]. Besides operating with largely lacking ground truthing under wet conditions most approaches perform rather similar [169]. [57] showed finally that the usually consulted $I(\theta)$ hyperbola (Eq. (23)) is not steep enough towards the dry end - therefore many authors had changed the parameterization to match the respective soil moisture ranges. This approach, however, questioned the overall validity of the method. The UTS intensity relation [57] was presented as a solution for that tension. Remarkably, UTS was already used implicitly in the earlier works of the authors [55, 56, 59] and is embedded in the horizontal and vertical footprint weighting functions. The often carried out procedure of calibrating W_{86}/D_{86} -weighted samples using in combination with the N0 equation had already indirectly improved the prediction quality of N0-based soil moisture retrievals by that UTS-based weighting. Furthermore, as [57] and [135, 171] had shown, it is also possible to derive a generalized intensity-soil moisture relation. This becomes evident if all corrections, weightings and instrumental effects are better understood and more precisely known.

2.10.4. Detection Technologies

The detector itself plays a crucial role in the assessment of soil moisture. All available detectors on the market have slightly different energy-dependent response functions, which lead to slightly different detection characteristics. [24] had presented a first evaluation of various systems and presented an understanding to which extend there are variations of the detector sensitivity. Yet, beyond the available devices from manufacturers researchers presented own modifications for example for roving [84, 143] or directional sensitivity [83]. For this type of neutron detector most models lack a technically robust description which is a requirement to evaluate the soil moisture relation. Empirically, however, such can only be measured in quasi-monoenergetic neutron reference fields [172]. A methodology for such instrumental characterizations has not yet been agreed on. Likewise, instrumental effects such as dead time and separation from signal to noise must be accounted for. The long-term performance can be affected by temperature variations, electronic drift and sensor aging - any change in the shape of the pulse height spectrum can lead to count-rate changes of the detector that are not attributed to changes in the environmental water content.

2.10.5. Uncertainties

A major limitation of CRNS lies in the low natural cosmic-ray neutron flux. The resulting statistical uncertainty directly limits the temporal resolution, which is typically on the order of hours. The achievable hourly precision greatly depends on the sensor location. The cosmic neutron flux increases exponentially with altitude, non-linearly with latitude, and decreases with the average moisture content. CRNS instrument manufacturers offer a wide range of systems that differ in normalized count rates - with, however, no agreed on standard defined but

often referenced to 10 % soil moisture at sea level. The instrument power can differ by as much as a factor of ten for stationary sensors, while mobile systems feature even higher count rates. Hence, the sensor choice, location and expected moisture content limit the desired temporal resolution. In literature, most researchers refer to the Poissonian nature of the neutron counter by assuming Gaussian statistics for the error estimation. Yet, the final uncertainty is determined by the soil-moisture-to-intensity-relation, instrument effects and uncertainties in the correction procedures. In order to advance the CRNS methodology the development of a metrological framework is necessary, including primary and secondary transfer standards. Such could for example ensure SI-traceable point-scale volumetric soil moisture measurements with uncertainties not exceeding 5 %. With target uncertainties in CRNS reaching 3 % in many studies the precision of the method is significantly improving over the last years. Such a framework needs to also include robust mathematical models, detailed neutron transport simulations, neutron detector characterizations and validation procedures of existing devices or potential future sensors. Based on that CRNS has the potential to become the most representative and precise method for integrally measuring soil moisture.

2.10.6. Metrology and standardisation

Standardisation has become particularly important as CRNS has moved from experimental setups to operational monitoring networks. Differences in detector design, moderation, shielding, data processing and calibration strategies currently hinder the interoperability of CRNS sites and complicate the fusion of CRNS-derived soil moisture with in-situ and remote-sensing products. By formulating a set of agreed on procedures and harmonized protocols a practical CRNS best-practices guide or generalized theoretical framework is expected to improve the consistency of CRNS measurements across networks and climates. Previous efforts by the International Atomic Energy Agency [173] have laid out the basis but require to be extended to support the use of CRNS in hydrological modelling, agricultural decision support, data fusion and climate services.

The SoMMet (Soil Moisture METrology) project is a recent European initiative that aims to establish a metrological foundation for soil moisture measurements across multiple spatial scales, from point sensors to satellite products. Its objective is to develop SI-traceable, interoperable methods and an infrastructure for the harmonisation of soil moisture measurements from decimetres up to kilometres [174]. This includes improving the quantification of the measurement uncertainty, characterizing detectors in reference neutron fields and calibration protocols for in-situ sensors. Within Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing, SoM-Met specifically addresses the lack of common calibration and validation practices. The project develops and tests traceable calibration procedures for CRNS, validates and benchmarks neutron transport models before transferring this knowledge to field conditions.

3. Conclusion

Today, Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing stands as the convergence of nuclear and particle physics into environmental sciences for developing a novel method to monitor soil moisture, a variable that has long been under-sampled relative to its importance. Soil moisture is a critical variable for agricultural productivity, ecosystem health, and climate dynamics, yet, its measurement remains fraught with challenges of scale, precision, and harmonization. CRNS has emerged as a novel tool, bridging the gap between point-scale measurements and satellite-derived products by providing real-time, spatially integrated estimates across hectares and depths of up to 50 cm. Its non-invasive nature and low maintenance have led to its integration in major monitoring networks (e.g. COSMOS, TERENO). The last ten years have seen strong advancements in theoretical understanding, precision and dedicated tools. Its growing popularity sparked the development of an own set of environmental instrumentation and Monte Carlo tools. Finally, the transition from helium-3-based detectors to cost-effective alternatives has enabled pathways for CRNS solutions to be integrated into a wide range of applications like irrigation management. Metrological initiatives such as the SoMMet consortium address the needs for standardisation to improve data reliability in this context. However, challenges persist under conditions where the large footprint and complex neutron transport may hinder a precise enough verification. Future efforts will focus on refining correction models for biomass, irrigation, and soil variability as well as harmonizing CRNS with other methods to resolve multi-scale soil moisture dynamics.

Author Contribution

M.K. contributed to all aspects of this work, including conceptualization, methodology, investigation, formal analysis, writing – original draft, and writing – review and editing.

Competing Interests

M.K. holds a CEO position at StyX Neutronica GmbH, Germany.

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